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Local authority in Homa bay, Kenya, during Jomo Kenyatta's first republic, 1963-1978

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Abstract

This paper examines the development of local authority in Homa Bay during the first republic of President Jomo Kenyatta. It has considered the restructuring and rebuilding of the nation, examined the changes that affected civil servants in local authority's governance, analyzed the provincial administration and the chief's tenure in Homa Bay, assessed the place of the 1966 Hardacre Commission, investigated development of infrastructures in Homa Bay (1960-66), reviewed the 1969 political crisis, examined the South Nyanza development plans and the role of NGOs in development in Homa Bay. The paper used the structural-functional theory in the understanding of the structures of local authorities' governance in Kenya. The functioning of a system determines the classification of a system. The methodology was based on qualitative approach whereby data collection was done through purposive sampling and analysis done by coding the responses from participants thematically. The results of this research would inform policy making by the state in matters pertaining to local authority governance and devolution.

Keywords: Local Authority; Civil servants; Structural functionalism; Development plans; System

1. Introduction

This paper sort to examine the place of local authorities during the tenure of Jomo Kenyatta, Kenya's founding President. The paper assumes that local authorities' governance from the outset remained divisive as the central government sought to check the influence of local authorities. The paper based its analysis on the views of authors renowned in matters pertaining to public governance in Kenya, the South Nyanza District Annual Reports, and the euphoria resulting from the declaration of independence in Kenya, regionalism and the functions of chiefs in the administrative issues within the council. It also discussed the changes that affected local authority governance in Homa Bay in the Kenyatta era.

The Hardcare Commission and infrastructural Development of Homa Bay were also discussed. Matters of education during the regime of Jomo Kenyatta have also been discussed in this paper since education is hallmark to the development agenda of any government in power. The independent government did not change much the way the local authorities were supposed to be ran since they still maintained a strong executive control.

The map shows the location of Homa Bay municipality earmarked for the Strategic Urban Development Plan (2008-2030).

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Figure 1 location of Homa Bay municipality map

2. Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on structural functional theory which states that; different institutions and structures in a society form a function like part of a social machine. Functionalism is also known as the consensus theory and because of that, it doesn't look at the inequalities that Marxism looks at such as exploitation, conflict between the bourgeoisie and the proletariat the two main classes according to Marx.

Structural functionalists believe that society leans towards equilibrium and social order. They see society like a human body, in which important organs to keep the society/body healthy and well. Social health means the same as social order, and is guaranteed when nearly everyone accepts the general moral values of their society. Hence structural functionalists believe the aim of key institutions, such as education, is to socialize children and teenagers. Socialization is the process by which the new generation learns the knowledge, attitudes and values that they will need as productive citizens [1].

Talcott Parsons, one of the architectures of this theory, was concerned with the integration of structure and process, and defined a social system as comprised of the interactions of many individuals within a situation, where the system

itself includes commonly understood cultural norms. These cultural norms are within a system of generalized symbols and their associated meanings (Parsons, 1951). These social systems have parts, or subsystems of varying complexity, that represent organizational structures. Additionally, social structures have social functions, which are the consequences of any social pattern for the operation of society as a whole. For Parsons, society is a complex system whose parts work together to promote solidarity and stability (they strive for equilibrium), and hence he defines the social structure as any relatively stable pattern of social behavior. An analysis of the social system is thus a consideration of ordered processes of change in the interactive patterns of actors within a structure (the norms behind the goals and means). Actors have status roles or positions within the structure itself, and in relation to other actors via interactions. However, these statuses and roles are units of the social system, and are not qualities of the actors themselves.

Those with high achievement will be trained for the most important jobs and in reward, be given the highest incomes. Those who achieve the least, will be given the least demanding jobs, and hence the least income (Munro, 1997). According to Sennet and Cobb however, “to believe that ability alone decides who is rewarded is to be deceived”. Meighan agrees, stating that large numbers of capable students from working class backgrounds fail to achieve satisfactory standards in school and therefore fail to obtain the status they deserve. Jacob believes this is because the middle class cultural experiences that are provided at school may be contrary to the experiences working-class children receive at home. Yet the structural functionalist perspective maintains that this social order, this continuity, is what most people desire.

The weakness of this perspective thus becomes evident. Why would the working class wish to stay working class? Such an inconsistency demonstrates that another perspective may be useful.

Some local authorities have weak financial bases in Kenya. If they do not get enough financial support from the central government, then such local authorities cannot offer good service delivery to the residents. There the structural functionalism insistence on ability for reward needs reconstruction.

The structural functional theory was ideal for the understanding of the subject area for this study. Municipalities are arranged in hierarchical manner with every section or department relating with one another vertically and horizontally. Development services in Homa Bay can only work better when all the officers tasked with service delivery and development matters work together in harmony. When there is consensus, services are likely to be provided without being undermined because all sections are involved in the planning and implementation of activities.

3. Restructuring and Rebuilding the Nation

The emerging monolithic perception of political life had a direct effect on the nature and character of the political system. The new regimes at once began to introduce practices that made it difficult for opposition parties to operate freely (Oyugi W. and Gitonga A. (ed) p.45). The independence government of Kenya expressed commitment to sound local government as well, expressing the expectations that it would play a more significant role than that assigned it prior to independence. The old functions of control and the provisions of basic services were to be expanded: local authorities were to be partners with the central government in national development.[2]. (Stamp, P. African Studies Review, 18).

The expectations regarding local government being so high was due in part to the excitement surrounding independence and the naive optimism that is so well reflected in the political studies of the independence era. [3].

The year 1963 had been the most eventful and memorable year in the past political history, not of Homa Bay, South Nyanza alone, but for the whole Kenya. The introduction of a complex, controversial and unfamiliar regionalism constitution, elections in May of leaders to the National parliament, Regional Assemblies, and the county councils on the system of “one man one vote”, followed by the attainment of internal self-government in June, and later by the most peaceful transfer of power from the British colonial Administration on December 12th, to the popularly elected Government of Kenya, clearly marked the realization of the political aims of the African people, the birth of our new nation and the end of an arduous political struggle by the Kenyans.

At Homa Bay over 40,000 people including Government officials from Tanganyika attended our Uhuru celebrations. South Nyanza elected six members and a senator to the National Parliament, eight members to the regional assembly and one Samuel Ayodo was appointed Minister for Local Government while Odero Jowi was appointed parliamentary Secretary to the Ministry of Labor and Social Services.

With the achievement of independence, the electors expected their hopes of better living standards, free education for their children, employment and free medical services to be met. The poorest section of the community and a large group of youth wingers wanted to see an immediate revolution accompanied by plentiful money for all. The call by the elected leaders for hard work, respect and obedience to the African Government did not in itself appear to satisfy the majority of the citizens. Despite all that the public officers of all departments and the chiefs continued to do their work well and enjoyed a rescannable amount of support and respect from the citizens [4].

But these expectations were going to be short lived since the central government out of fear that the local government might shortchange it were they to be allowed to enjoy full autonomy resorted to other means, financial or otherwise to curtail the influence of local authorities over the management of public affairs at local government levels. In respect of this, Rodger (1996, 506) argues:

Their financial disarray, matched by a failure to efficiently deliver services, provided central government with the rationale for assuming most of their powers and responsibilities. Most notably, the Transfer of Functions Act of 1970 deprived County Councils of their role in providing health care, and all but Municipalities of the task of providing primary education. Meanwhile, further assumption of revenue-raising powers by central government resulted in further erosion of the fiscal base of local authorities, which none the less earned the blame for the non-delivery of services

3.1. Changes that affected civil Servants in Local Authorities Governance

In conformity with the relevant regulations and in the interests of maintaining proper discipline in the Government service, civil servants were henceforth debarred from standing for elections as member of local authorities. A civil servant serving as an elected member of any local authority would be required to resign forthwith his membership of the local authority concerned and should he/she fail to do so, he/she would be called upon to resign his/her appointment and cease to be a member of the public service[5].

The restructuring of local authorities affected the operations of Homa Bay during the period. People were nominated to fill vacancies in local councils left by resigning of county councilors prompted by disqualification of the County Councilors. The new Councilors were then sworn in at the next full Council meeting. In that respect, Ezekiel Ochieng Ongaga and Hesbon Nyawinda were sworn in as new councilors for Kanyada 1 and Kanyada 11 wards in Homa Bay (Circular from A.R.G.A. Central Division Ref 3/11/Vol.11/262). All the secretaries, Area and Local Councils were duly informed of the changes of Memberships of Local Councils that in accordance with Local Government (Nyanza Region) (County of South Nyanza) (Amendment) Order 1964, accordingly, all County Council members ceased to be members of Area or Local Councils with effect from 23rd June, 1964.

The arrangement would not preclude the Minister for Local Government from exercising his prerogative to nominate civil servants to local authorities (Personnel Circular No.43 dated 19/10/6, Director of Personnel). He told them that the effective date for resignation would be notified to them. The information was expected to be cascaded to the divisions.

3.2. The Provincial Administration and the chief's Tenure in Homa Bay

In the maintenance of law and order, the South Nyanza Annual Report, 1963 stated that the Kenya Police worked hand in hand with the Provincial Administration and the relationship between the Kenya Police and the citizens were good. Besides the police, the judiciary had been well established in Homa bay with a new court house being erected. The transfer of the African Courts to the judicial department was concluded in July and a registrar of African Courts was appointed a third class magistrate. Crime remained at a steady figure but the commonest of all were petty thieving and assaults on persons. There were a few murders caused by excessive drinking of Nubian gin and opium smoking.

In 1964, the Provincial Administration was transferred to the Office of the President. In concentrating power in his office and in particular, in promoting the central coordinating role to the provincial administration, Kenyatta faced considerable opposition. The instrument he employed to address that opposition was the Provincial Administration, a government department that had never been under the Governor's or Chief Secretaries' office during the entire colonial period. District commissioners used to be the chairmen of Local councils with full executive powers but this position was reversed when District commissioners were removed from chairmanship and Local Authorities given full executive powers. The District Commissioners retained an advisory role but, in most cases, this was practically ineffective. Thus, the regional constitution gave the Local Authorities an enhanced status, which almost amounted to virtual autonomy. The logical consequence of Kenyatta's action was to make Provincial Administration an agent, in fact the executive arm

of the ruling party, KANU. Thereafter both the party and parliament were in fact subsumed under the president, with the Provincial Administration holding sway (Kipkorir B, 2010).

This study examined the history of some chiefs who served in Homa Bay in the colonial and post-colonial eras.

The chiefs were Samwel Ogoma, Odoyo and later Homa Bay had a Chief for the town known as Tukiko Oyare, followed by Agutu Rapudo who lost his job because of allegations of alcoholism around 1985[6].

The Chief for Homa Bay town at the time of this research was Senior Chief Joshua Chwanya Ochogo, who was the first respondent the researcher contacted. The chiefs in Homa Bay, like elsewhere in Kenya, existed and obtained their powers in the Provincial Administration under the "*Chiefs' Act*". Some respondents saw them in democratic terms, while those opposed to them saw them as an anachronistic institution, which lacked legitimacy because chiefs were not elected.

But in certain cases some chiefs and sub-chiefs encountered great difficulties in their work. There were some low level leaders and people who had expected to see immediate dismissals of their chiefs and sub-chiefs regardless of ability, age and education. Some chiefs were unable to adjust themselves to rapidly changing circumstances. That state of affairs led, in some cases, to a virtual collapse of good government, on-payment of rates and a deplorable lack of social and economic progress. There were other chiefs who enjoyed mass popularity at the expense of progress in their location. On the whole, the generally good and high morale of the chiefs and their assistants was shaken by rapid political changes. Constant changes of District Commissioners and District Officers as well as other departmental officers resulted deplorably in serious lack of continuity and slow progress [7]. Chiefs also assisted in advising the people on good agricultural practices for boosting food production for food security within their jurisdiction. The 1963 report documented that agriculturally, the District remained backward owing partly to frequent changes of officers and the general self-complacency of the inhabitants. Total rainfall for the year recorded at Homa bay was 51.34mm and December was the wettest month in the year. If people could make efforts to dig their "shambas" and plant cotton early as advised by the cotton Board and the Agricultural staff South Nyanza could easily produce cotton worth 3 million shillings annually.

Just as the president exercised his political authority by ruling via prominent regional leaders who were given measure of independence, so did he exercise control over the Provincial Administration by granting P.C.s almost unlimited authority. Indeed, in Kenyatta's state, they were virtually lords in their own realms provided they administered their fiefs efficiently on the regimes behalf. [8].

In conclusion, Chiefs in Homa Bay worked very well with other stakeholders in the provision of services to the residents despite difficulties associated with their work during the colonial period and even after independence. They mobilized the people for various projects at the grassroots. They also sensitized the people on various government policies besides being in charge of security issues.

But of significance was the fact that up to the time of Kenyatta's death in 1978, chiefs were required to toe the KANU party line something they did with gusto.

3.3. Hardacre Commission (1966)

Between 1964 and 1970, the government continued with its efforts to establish a more elaborate and effective organizational structure for the development policy making process within the executive. By the end of the first decade of independence, these efforts had resulted to the establishment of Central Government and Provincial Organizational Structures for public policy formulation and management by the executive. Executive, Cabinet council of economic ministers, Economic Planning and Development and planning units within various ministries (Jackson, 1970, 184) Provincial Development Committees in all provinces and District Development Committees in all Districts had been put in place to articulate the governing agenda at both the central and the local government levels (Moi, 1984, 31-32).

This Report of the Local Government Commission of Inquiry of 1966 was chaired by W.S. Hardacre with members; Robert S. Matano, J.Mwangi and Bethwel A. Ogot. This committee received over 150 memoranda, not only from ministries and local authorities, but also from various organizations and private individuals. They heard oral evidence from over 100 of these in Nairobi and at various places throughout Kenya. Their terms of reference were published as Gazette Notice No.1007 of 22nd March 1966, and were as follows; the composition and constitution of local authorities; the mandatory and permissive functions of local authorities; whether certain services at present which were the responsibility of local authorities should be provided by other bodies and, if so, the nature and constitution of such

bodies; the extent and nature of central government control over local authorities; the general financial situation of local authorities including their taxation potential and how revenue to meet the cost of services provided by them should be raised and from what sources; the extent and nature of Government contributions to local authorities; the means of strengthening the quality and security of local authority staff, including appointments and discipline; allowances (if any) to be made to members of local authorities; generally, the means of improving the capacity of local authorities to contribute towards the implementations of the National Development.

President Kenyatta appointed the Hardcare commission in march 1966 to inquire into local government and gave it a very broad mandate to make recommendations; but after he received its report, he angrily turned away from it and proceeded to act the way he must have intended all along. Looking back today, it is clear that he was concerned about the galvanizing part but, alas, not the 'democratic' one. It was not his desire to increase the democratic space; the opposite was his intent (Kipkorir, 2010)

3.4. Infrastructures in Homa Bay (1960-66)

The country had just attained her independence. People in Homa Bay and the whole country were enthusiastic for development and they expected commitment from their government to tackle the infrastructural challenges facing them. Because this period was not marked by any serious global economic problems, infrastructural development was possible. The only limitation was the absence of a robust private sector. The government alone could not meet all the infrastructural needs of the residents. It was therefore important that private capital be tapped to make the much needed infrastructural development of Homa Bay that would offer significant investment opportunities for local traders.

During this period, the government maintained roads by self-help schemes. Many councils lacked roads, railways, access to electricity, clean water for drinking and sanitation. In Homa Bay, road development was given priority way back in the 60s. One of the roads was started by a self-help group as a short link between Homa Bay and Ogande School. The Road started from Got Rabuor School, crosses River Rangwena behind Asego Hill and met Ogande Road behind Kabunde Chiefs Office Camp. It was estimated that the cost of bridging Rangwena would be about \$40. The Road is about two miles long. Most of the Health Assistants did not like to work in their own Location because they felt that they could do much better when working in other locations. The government asked Chiefs to make provisions in their area council estimates so that at least one semi-permanent building would be put up for the Location Health Assistants at the Chief's Camp.[9]. Development of infrastructure in Homa Bay involved their leaders in government and in the civilian population. It was not easy to wait for the government to initiate all infrastructural developments without the people being involved in the planning and executions of such developments.

Homa Bay high school and Homa Bay district hospital were built in 1964 and 1965. The new state required time to settle down in order to plan for development of infrastructure that was expected to spur development of Homa Bay and the entire country. The building of more infrastructures could have been significantly achieved if the council through the national government had sought assistance from development partners such as China, India and Arab countries.[10].

3.5. The 1969 Political Crisis

The year had been to Kenya, and therefore, no less to South Nyanza, Homa Bay, a year of a historical and peaceful political revolution. The banning of the K.P.U., the registration of voters and the General Elections at the close of the year were the milestones in this political trend. The political trend was unique in two remarkable aspects. First, she mourned, with 'perhaps' more pronounced bitterness than elsewhere in Kenya, the loss of her own Rusinga-born political hero and Minister for Economic Planning and Development, Tom Mboya which led to a temporary but tense tribal animosity between the Luo and Kikuyu arising from suspicion surrounding the assassination. Secondly, the primary and Presidential elections proved an exit for all the former and Honorable members of parliament (South Nyanza District Annual Report: 1969, 2).

No major political meetings were held in 1970. Most of the licensed meetings were of social nature rather than a political one. This may mean the end of transitional period or a new era. Secret meetings met a death aftermath of the KPU. But even so the year 1970 had an important event on record-a visit to Gatundu-to pay a courtesy-call on President Kenyatta by a delegation from Homa bay to present a memorandum to him stating their grievances and suggestions toward better Nation Building (South Nyanza Annual Report, 1970). The year 1975 was a quite one in Homa Bay and the entire South Nyanza District as far as political activities were concerned.[11].

3.6. South Nyanza Development Plans During Kenyatta era

In sharp contrast to GEMA nation, Nyanza (i.e. the home of the Luo ethnic group) suffered severe repression and neglect, more than any other province for trying to challenge and question the unjust enrichment of one region on what was a 'national cake'. We give a few illustrations with regard to the ethnic suppressions during the Kenyatta regime. In 1966, Oginga Odinga, the undoubted Luo leader, who had hitherto been the Vice President of the nation, and the ruling party, Kenya African National Union (KANU), lost both posts at the famous Limuru Party Conference. The message was clear but milder at this point in time. Odinga responded by forming his political party - The Kenya Peoples Union (KPU). The accusations and counter-accusations between Odinga and Kenyatta over KPU were largely emotive and it succeeded in heightening Luo-Kikuyu ethnic animosities that sometimes degenerated into open confrontations.

The assassinations of Tom Joseph Mboya (i.e. a Luo) for motives never fully ascertained on July 9, 1969, a few months after the mysterious death of Argwings Kodhek, another prominent Luo politician, intensified the ethnic animosity between the Luo and the Kikuyu. The banning of KPU in October 1969 and the detention of Odinga and other leaders without trial sent wrong signals to the Luo ethnic group who could not hide their emotions and anger during the visit of Kenyatta to Kisumu. During this visit, a large crowd of Luo's reportedly menaced Kenyatta's security and was fired on by the security guards in what later came to be known as the 'Kisumu massacre' where tens of people lost their lives (see page 159). In an explanatory statement, the government accused KPU of being subversive, intentionally stirring up inter-ethnic strife, and accepting foreign money to promote anti-national activities.

The proscription in effect brought a return of Kenya to the single party state, following these incidents, Nyanza province, like other non-Kikuyu areas, was virtually written off from 'national' development plans. For instance, the government terminated the construction the Kenya-Uganda highway (part of a Trans Africa highway system) in 1969 because the road had reached Luoland. The plans to construct the Yala falls hydro-electric plant was also brought to a halt for spurious reasons.[12]

The National Development Plan in respect to the South Nyanza, with Homa Bay being the headquarters, elicited debate in parliament on 12th - May 24th, 1974 in a motion that was moved by Member of Parliament for Kasipul Kabondo, Ezekiel Mbori Yogo who stated that:

I would now like to turn to the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning and say that South Nyanza is three times bigger than Busia District. Is it not surprising when I reveal to the House that large as it is South Nyanza does not have a single Commercial bank to serve wananchi? I remember that in 1972 I raised many questions on this issue. What is happening is that the businessmen, farmers and teachers in South Nyanza, to mention only a few, have to travel miles away to Kisii or Kisumu to seek banking facilities. I plead for only one commercial bank. There was no mention made to this in the 1974/78 Development Plan. A white Sugar factory for South Nyanza has been a story in this country for many years and has been mentioned since 1971. I am appealing to the ministry of Commerce and Industry to speed up the establishment of a white sugar factory in South Nyanza because it has already been approved.[13].

The MP for Kasipul Kabondo commended the President for his decree on free primary education from Standard one to Standard two. He stressed that ordinary person did not realize that Kenya had independence until this year when Universal Primary Education extended to all parts of the country. To him, it was important that the development plan should include all the rural areas because the towns of this country had already enjoyed treated water, beautiful roads and beautiful cars, large houses and many other facilities but the person who lived in the rural area had nothing to enjoy and, therefore, nothing to be proud of. He further argued that the Development Plan should have concentrated in providing such facilities to the people living in the rural areas.

Although Mbori put a strong case for South Nyanza as a whole, and Homa Bay by extension in terms of the need to have banking facilities and sugar factory, his assertion that by 1974 all towns in Kenya had good roads and other better facilities was fallacious. For a long time Homa Bay municipality did not have piped water and good roads. Residents relied on hand carted water supplied by hand cart vendors and some roads within the municipality were poorly maintained and hence impassable especially during the rainy season.

Homa Bay was one of the 38 urban centers which were designated for the urban housing programme during the 1974/78 plan period (SNDDP 1974/78). There was nothing however on the ground to show. To make matters worse, the Kenyatta and Odinga's political differences permeated to the local levels for a long time. Homa Bay was part of Luo Nyanza believed to have been alienated from development by the Kenyatta administration. Funding to Homa Bay council from the central government was curtailed thereby affecting service delivery to the resident population. The region had embraced Kenya Peoples Union (KPU) and not interested in KANU politics anymore.[14].

Luo Nyanza was poor not because her people are lazy or frivolous. In my evaluation that was informed by my experience in the banking sector and other interactive activities, the toughest workers in this economy come from this region. The area was in want not because it lacked indigenous professionals who are qualified in relevant fields. Indeed, on a per capita basis, few regions could then equal the Luo in educational and professional attainment (Kipkorir, 2010).

I agree with Kipkorir in his view about the low level of development in Nyanza including that of Homa Bay. Homa Bay municipality bore the brunt of neglect by the central government. The entire Luo Nyanza over the years was pushed to the periphery in terms of development because the region was perceived to be anti-government ever since Odinga disagreed with Kenyatta. For many years later, the Luo Nyanza remained in opposition politics where they continued to fight for their voices to be heard and they called for political change that would be inclusive in terms of political and economic powers. During the struggle for constitutional change, most agitators fought for devolution clauses to be included in the new constitution. But the point to note is that devolution even in the country that adopted it long ago acknowledged that it had its own shortcomings.

3.7. NGOs in Homa Bay – Kenyatta era

The most active groups operating Non-Governmental Organizations in Homa Bay during the Kenyatta era were: Kenya Red Cross Society, Care International and USAID. According to Mzee Walter Chwanya, these NGOs assisted people in matters of hygiene/health services, disaster management and environmental conservation. He said that the Kenyatta government did not interfere with their operations.

Source: The Author, guided by CAP 265 Laws of Kenya (Old Constitution).

Figure 2 Organography for local government linkages

4. Research methodology

The target population such as the chiefs, councilors and some residents were interviewed, and in my opinion, they gave me information that made my studies a success. The theory of structural functionalism helped to understand how the Provincial Administration and the municipal council structures work in tandem for the sake of development and service delivery to the residents of Homa Bay municipality. Ethical issues were considered and that was the reason the research sought for permission from the National Council of Science and Technology for authority to conduct this research.

The fact that the methodology followed the tenets of qualitative research, the analysis was done through the coding of responses in thematic manner before drawing conclusion on the objectives of the study.

5. Conclusion

From the colonial era, the Kenyatta administration inherited underdeveloped infrastructure and transportation networks. Poor and inefficient infrastructure undermined the economic development even in the local authorities and Homa Bay municipality was not exceptional. Homa Bay municipality just like other municipalities suffered from strong central control during Kenyatta era since he was reluctant to devolve full autonomy to local authorities. The structure of the municipality in Kenya was such that the executive wielded a lot of power over local elected officials, the councilors. This affected service delivery and development because the council could not act on its own in effecting development agenda for the council. Even the executive appointed Hardacre commission, made very little impact on the way the council was being governed. Roads in Homa Bay were still in pathetic conditions thereby inhibiting the growth and development of the municipality. Most commissions were appointed to serve at the whims of the executive which was usually not under obligations to implement the reports of such commissions.

The Kenyatta government was not able to address the problems by channeling investments towards expanding infrastructures in local authorities across the country. Infrastructures in Homa Bay during the Kenyatta era remained largely neglected and therefore even with its position as the oldest town in South Nyanza, it was not growing despite the potential it held. Governance weaknesses resulting from political misunderstandings between the Luo leadership at the local levels and national government under Mzee Kenyatta, undermined the growth of Homa Bay despite the fact that the council was endowed with natural resources. The South Nyanza Development Plans during the Kenyatta era were undermined by the political rivalries between Kenyatta and Jaramogi Odinga despite the great issues in the plan lack of implementation ensured that little development took place in Homa Bay for a long time.

This study also concerned with the governance of local authorities after Kenyatta but under the 2nd Republic of Daniel Arap Moi through his “Nyayo Philosophy”. Relationship between the Provincial Administration and local Authorities’ Governance in the “Nyayo” era was put in focus.

The study further concerned itself with effects of South Nyanza Development Plan on the municipal governance of Homa Bay Municipality and the change in education and the introduction of free primary milk under Moi government.

Compliance with ethical standards

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